

500 nm is 7140 with Sandell's sensitivity $0.01 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. The average and relative standard deviations were 0.005 and 0.7 per cent respectively.

The ions which do not interfere at all concentrations are Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , ClO_4^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , F^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-} , $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7^{3-}$, Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ag^+ , Sn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , and Pd^{2+} . The ions which seriously interfere are Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} (± 2 percent in absorbance value was arbitrarily taken as an interference).

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Studies in Terpenes : Part XXXIX : *m*-Menth-1-en-8-ol, A constituent of Wallach's Sylveterpineol

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THE two *m*-terpineols comprising Wallach's sylveterpineol have been declared as *m*-menth-6-en-8-ol (1) and *m*-menth-1-en-8-ol (2) based on the examination of oxidation products.^{1,2} Spectroscopic data backing structure (1) were presented by us earlier.^{3,4} We would like to report now further evidence which sheds light on the isomeric constituent (2).

Repetition of the esterification of Wallach's sylveterpineol [b.p. $90^\circ\text{--}92^\circ$ (5 mm)] with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride according to published procedure⁵ gave a benzoate, m.p. 66° , $(\alpha)_D^{30} + 38.4^\circ$ (c 1.2, CHCl_3). (Found : C, 67.61; H, 7.17; N, 5.15. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires : C, 67.26; H, 6.99; N, 4.62%). Saponification was effected by heating a mixture of the ester (10 g), ether (25 ml), methanol (70 ml) and potassium hydroxide (7 g) for 1 hr; usual work-up followed by steam distillation afforded an oil (4.6 g), b.p. $88.5^\circ\text{--}92.5^\circ$ (5 mm), $n_D^{20} + 1.4814$, d_{30}^{30} 0.9306, $(\alpha)_D^{30} + 46.24^\circ$ [Lit.⁵ b.p. 84° (3 mm)], n_D^{20} 1.4838, d_4^{20} 0.9373, $(\alpha)_D^{20} + 46.20^\circ$]. Thin layer chromatography [adsorbent : Silica gel G; developer : benzene-methanol (10 : 1); indicator : vanillin (5%) in concd. sulphuric acid] disclosed that the oil contained two components with R_f 0.62 and 0.52, of which the former R_f was identified as due to (1) by co-chromatography with a genuine sample. A homogeneous specimen of the required constituent was prepared from the oil by gas-liquid chromatography on a 15 ft column of 20% Silicone oil—DC 550 on Chromosorb-W, 60–80 mesh, temp. 165° , hydrogen pressure 15 p.s.i. utilising Aerograph A 90-P₃ Model; R_f 0.56 (Found : C, 77.95; H, 11.50. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{17}\text{OH}$ requires : C, 77.87; H, 11.76%). $\gamma_{\text{max}}^{\text{neat}}$ 3400 and 1150 cm^{-1} , ($\rightarrow$ C—OH), 1375 and 1365 cm^{-1} , [(CH_3)₂C <, doublet] and 1667 and 820 cm^{-1} (> C = CH—).

Proof for the structure of the above alcohol as *m*-menth-1-en-8-ol (2) was provided by the 60 MHz PMR spectra from CDCl_3 (Fig. 1). The C_9 and C_{10} methyl protons featured as singlet at δ 1.20 and

Fig. 1. Partial 60 MHz PMR spectra of *m*-menth-1-en-8-ol.

the C_1 methyl protons as singlet at δ 1.66. The ring proton at C_2 was visible as a broad singlet at δ 5.40 (curve a). Irradiation at δ 5.40 did not influence the high field pattern in any significant manner. In particular the peak at δ 1.66. In the reverse experiment, however, the broad featureless signal at δ 5.40 sharpened up to something like a six-line pattern, doublet of triplet (curve b) which one would expect due to coupling to protons in positions 3 and 6.

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Studies on Hydroxamic Acids : Part I Separation and Gravimetric Determination of Barium using N-m-Tolyl-m-Nitrobenzohydro- xamic Acid

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THE hydroxamic acids are found useful reagents for carrying out gravimetry¹⁻⁵, spectrophotometry⁶⁻⁹ and for other analytical techniques^{10,11}. Some methods for gravimetric determination of barium were reported earlier¹²⁻¹⁴. But no such systematic method has so far been reported for separation and gravimetric determination of barium. This method is most suitable for the separation and gravimetric determination of barium. The N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid reacts with barium chloride solution to give a complete precipitation of barium in presence of Ag⁺, Mn⁺², Cu⁺², Ni⁺², Cd⁺², Zn⁺², Hg⁺², Pd⁺², Be⁺², Ga⁺³, Sb⁺³, As⁺³, Bi⁺³, Ti⁺⁴, Zr⁺⁴, V⁺⁵, Mo⁺⁶ and UO₂⁺², Pr⁺³, Nd⁺³ and Sm⁺³ at pH 2.5-3.0, adjusted by hydrochloric acid and ammonium hydroxide. The purity of the complex was checked by I.R., U.V. and elemental analysis.

Experimental

Chemicals :

All the chemicals used were of G.R. and AnalaR grades of E. Merck and B.D.H., respectively unless otherwise stated.

Reagents :

The aqueous stock solution of barium chloride was prepared by dissolving 1 g of barium chloride

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in a litre of double distilled water. The contents of barium were determined volumetrically¹⁵ and a stock solution of the 0.001M concentration was prepared by appropriate dilution.

The complexing reagent, N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid (N-m-T-m-NBHA) was synthesized by the procedure described earlier¹⁶, m.p. 118° (reported 118°). The purity of the reagent was confirmed by T.L.C., I.R., and U.V. Spectra.

A 1% solution of masking agents was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in double distilled glass water.

Procedure :

In a litre beaker, 5 ml. of a 0.001M solution of barium chloride and about 400 ml. distilled water were heated at 60° on a steambath. The 10 ml of 0.1M of N-m-Tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid in alcohol was added dropwise with constant stirring followed by 0.001M ammonium hydroxide until complete precipitation was obtained. The pH 2.5-3.0 was adjusted by ammonium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid. The solution was digested for 2.30 mins. over a steam bath, filtered through a sintered glass crucible of the porosity G4 and washed thoroughly with hot water and finally with 20% alcohol water solution (5×4 ml). The barium complex thus obtained was dried at 110° and weighed as [C₁₄H₁₁N₂O₄]₂Ba.

Separation of Barium from commonly occurring Metal Ions and Rare Earths :

With a view to separate the barium from the other commonly occurring metal ions, a 5 ml of the 0.001M solution of barium chloride was mixed with a known amount of desired foreign metal ions and diluted to 250 ml. The pH was adjusted to 2.5-3.00 as usual with 0.01M ammonium hydroxide and 0.01M hydrochloric acid. A 5 ml portion of the 1% potassium cyanide solution was added and the content was heated upto 60° on a steambath. Then, the alcoholic solution of the reagent was added dropwise to it with constant stirring. The complex so formed was allowed to stand for ½ hr, on a steambath. Thus barium could be separated and precipitated quantitatively in presence of Ag⁺, Mn⁺², Cu⁺², Ni⁺², Cd⁺², Zn⁺², Hg⁺², Pd⁺² and V⁵. Barium can also be separated and precipitated quantitatively with N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid in presence of Be⁺², Ga⁺³, Sb⁺³, As⁺³, Bi⁺³, Ti⁺⁴ and Zr⁺⁴ as above by taking 10 ml of 1% citrate and oxalate as masking agents instead of cyanide.

Likewise, barium can also be separated and precipitated quantitatively in presence of UO₂⁺² and Mo⁺⁶ using mg-EDTA as the masking agents.

For the rare earths, the barium is successfully separated and precipitated quantitatively from La⁺³, Pr⁺³, Nd⁺³ and Sm⁺³ by adjusting the pH 2.5-3.0 because all these rare earths are precipitated above the pH 3.0.